

АСПЕКТЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ИННОВАЦИИ И ИНВЕСТИЦИИ НА ЖЕЛЕЗНОДОРОЖНОМ ТРАНСПОРТЕ.

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Directions for the development of railway transport are based on the forecast of the long-term socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Strategy of Actions for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, the message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis, from this point of view, "to organize road and rail transit hubs for through the construction of modern infrastructure with quality service"[1], legislative and other regulatory legal acts. This takes into account promising areas for the development of the economy and the social sphere of the regions, sectors of the economy, transport and logistics infrastructure, international transport integration, primarily within the framework of the Commonwealth of Independent States, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, as well as the experience of developing transport systems in countries with rapidly developing economies. "We believe that the China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan-Afghanistan railway with access to the ports of Pakistan and Iran, facing the Indian Ocean, could also be integrated into the extensive network of transport corridors of the "One Belt, One Road"[2]

The transport system of Uzbekistan has become a new connecting corridor between South and East Asian countries. Moreover, on this route, the distance of transportation between these countries is by sea, that is, through the strait in Southeast Asia. In 2016, the first railway container train from the eastern Chinese coastal province of Jiangsu, having covered over 2,550 km, arrived at the Uzbek-Afghan border[3].

For the first time in economics, the Austrian scientist J. Schumpeter described the essence of "innovation" as follows: "Innovation is a new look, an approach to an existing process and involves the use of a modern discovery, development or new production associated with human activity in a certain process"[4]. He introduced the concept of "innovation" to economic science, explaining the difference between the concepts of "economic growth" and "economic development": "Put as many mail coaches in a row as you wish, you will not get a railway" [5]. Thus, from the

point of view of J. Schumpeter, innovation is the emergence of something new, previously unknown (for example, railways), it is the emergence of innovation that serves economic development.

The Uzbek Railway, the second in the CIS (after the Moscow—St. Petersburg line with Sapsan trains in Russia), launched high-speed passenger train traffic ("Afrosiyob") on a special line rebuilt for this purpose from the capital Tashkent to the third largest city of Uzbekistan - Samarkand, which was then extended to Bukhara. Uzbekistan needs to unlock the potential of infrastructure investments. For example, in the field of railways. Their length in Uzbekistan is just over 6 thousand km, while in Japan it is 22 thousand km. This means that we have the opportunity to create a railway system, which requires infrastructure investments.

The main task of innovation policy is to identify and develop promising transportation technologies and safety and reliability systems, the creation of which would allow railway transport to reach a qualitatively new level of development, and in new economic and political conditions (market or mixed relations, dynamically changing tax and credit policies) to ensure its stable and efficient operation, the ability to to renewal and self-development, to meet the needs of the clientele. In our opinion, the choice of prospective technical means, methods of delivery or organization of transportation should be carried out from the perspective of comprehensive assessments of innovation on a wide range of criteria and possible consequences of application (environmental, social and economic).

The solution of such a problem is possible only if a fundamentally new methodology is created based on modern mathematical methods, models, theories focused on the use of advanced automated tools based on data banks, knowledge, expert systems. It is advisable to select the most promising technical means and evaluate innovations in the field of organization and management based on an integrated approach. At the same time, the following principles must be maintained.

The complexity of the technological chain "from door to door" or from the last technological operation of the sender to the first technological operation of the recipient, i.e. the rhythm and improvement of the technology of train, freight and sorting works of both mainline and industrial transport should be coordinated and focused on specific end results. In some cases, "elongated" technological chains are considered from the supply of raw materials for the production of manufactured products to its sale on the market.

1. Complexity from the standpoint of consistency and quality of execution of the main operations of the technological chain "door to door" with technological operations that ensure the transport process, for example, related to the maintenance of permanent railway devices

(overhead track structure, contact network, SCB facilities), repair work of rolling stock, etc. Here we are actually talking about coordination of the rhythm of the work of cargo moving technologies with technologies that ensure the effective functioning of the former.

2. Complexity from the point of view of compliance of technological parameters of the reinspective "through" transportation process with technical means, which should be understood not as individual means, for example, a single new type of wagon or locomotive, but as fleets of wagons or locomotives, chains of machines and mechanisms in the track economy, loading and unloading complexes, etc.

3. 1. In the conditions of the formation of market relations, the technological improvement of railways and their technical development should be considered in conjunction with the organizational, economic and legal mechanism that ensures the effective functioning of new technologies and the interest of all links participating in the "through" transportation process. It is quite obvious that in modern conditions of state independence, a detailed study of the issues of economic relations between the subjects of the transportation process will be required, the introduction of new principles and management structures that allow combining strategic planning with economic regulation of the development of transport complexes; redistribution of functions between independent states and other levels of railway transport management, as well as issues of tax, tariff, credit and marketing policy.

The development and modernization of railway infrastructure is carried out on the basis of the following principles:

- priority of modernization and development of existing capacities in comparison with new construction;
- alienation of land for transport needs in the optimal size, reduction of negative landscape changes and pollution of the natural environment;
- maximum use of railway transport facilities and communications to ensure domestic, foreign trade and transit traffic;
- linking the development of railway infrastructure with the development of engineering communications, energy, communications, water supply, and other infrastructure industries;
- coordination of infrastructure development of various modes of transport;
- development of infrastructure in accordance with the rational principles of urban planning and land use planning;
- specialization of the largest infrastructure facilities of similar purpose, prevention or restriction of competition of the largest infrastructure facilities;

- ensuring the necessary land reservation for the long-term development of the supporting transport network;
- maximum concentration of budgetary and attracted resources on priority projects and full acceleration of their implementation, including with the involvement of foreign borrowings for this purpose.

ЛИТЕРАТУРА:

1. Мирзиёев Ш.М Послание Президента Республики Узбекистан Шавката Мирзиёева Олий Мажлису. – Ташкент: ИПТД «Узбекистан», 2018.-С. 68
2. Мирзиёев Ш.М. Уверенно продолжим путь национального развития на новом этапе. – Ташкент: ИПТД «Узбекистан», 2018.-320 с.
3. Дороги и транспорт. Информационно-аналитический журнал. г. Москва, Россия. №10, 2016 г. С-34.
4. Шумпетер Й.А. Теория экономического развития. М.: Прогресс, 1983.с..278-285.
5. Цит. По: Логинова Н.А. Управление взаимодействиями на рынке транспортных услуг. СПб,: Изд-во СПбГИЭУ, 2012.